

A REVIEW PAPER ON MULTIPLE FACE RECOGNITION USING DEEP LEARNING METHODS – LBPH AND YOLOV7

Ms. Manisha S. Loharkar

Computer Engineering, MCOERC, Nashik
manishaloharkars@gmail.com

Prof. Shital S.Wagh

Computer Engineering, MCOERC, Nashik.
shital.wagh@matoshri.edu.in

Abstract:

The smart classroom leverages automation to streamline tasks like attendance registration, which traditionally requires significant time and effort. While methods such as identification cards, radio frequency, and biometric systems have been used, they often face challenges related to safety, accuracy, and cost. Recent advancements in digital image processing particularly face recognition technology, offer a promising alternative. This study developed an automated attendance system utilizing the YOLOv7 algorithm, which effectively detects and recognizes multiple faces simultaneously. Tested on a database of 31 students from Mustansiriyah University, the system achieved up to 100% accuracy, proving to be a reliable and efficient solution for automating attendance in classrooms. The proposed system is focused on marking the attendance automatically and generates analysis report. Recognition of human face is an important domain in unique identification of humans. This method is developing for taking attendance of students in a classroom which integrate the face detection technology.

Keywords: Face recognition, LBPH, YOLOv7, CNN

INTRODUCTION

Organizations have adopted various methods for Attendance Management Systems (AMS). While some still use traditional manual methods, others have transitioned to biometric techniques. [1] The manual approach can be cumbersome, especially in large classrooms, and calculating attendance percentages manually is time-consuming. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) offers high efficiency and hands-free access control but is prone to misuse. Biometric systems, such as fingerprint, retina, and voice recognition, provide solutions but have their own limitations.

To address these challenges, the proposed system uses a camera to capture images of students in the classroom [2]. Face detection is then applied to identify and extract faces from the images. These faces are clustered using a clustering algorithm, creating a training database. The system compares the clustered faces with the database, recording attendance for the recognized faces. If no match is found, new faces are added to the database, improving accuracy over time. This automated system, combining image processing and machine learning techniques, ensures efficient and accurate attendance management, saving time and resolving the issues match with ongoing methods [3]. A comparable problem arises with traditional attendance systems, where administrative staffs supply lecturers with a list of student names for manual attendance marking. This method not only consumes valuable

lecture time but also causes inconvenience for both students and lecturers. Errors can occur when students do not hear their names being called, leading to frustration for everyone involved. Furthermore, relying on paper-based attendance systems introduces security risks, as records can easily be lost or stolen. To overcome the limitations of traditional methods and the challenges posed by RFID and biometric techniques, an automated Attendance Management System (AMS) using face recognition technology is proposed. This system utilizes computer vision and machine learning to streamline and enhance the accuracy of attendance management.

The primary function of the proposed system is to capture images of students in the classroom using a camera. Once the images are captured, the system applies face detection algorithms to identify and extract faces from the scene. Face detection is an essential step in this process, as it isolates individual faces from the background and other non-relevant elements of the image. After detection, the faces are processed using a clustering algorithm, which groups similar faces together to create a training database. This database is dynamically updated as new faces are detected and added to the system. By clustering faces, the system minimizes errors in face recognition, ensuring that similar-looking faces are correctly classified. The system then matches the clustered faces with those in the existing database, automatically marking attendance for recognized faces. If a face does not match any in the current database, the system prompts the addition of the new face, further improving the accuracy of the system over time as it learns to recognize more individuals. This automated face recognition-based attendance system offers several advantages over traditional and biometric methods. First, it significantly reduces the time and effort required to take attendance, as the process is automated and requires minimal manual intervention. Second, it eliminates the possibility of misuse or fraud, as face recognition cannot be easily bypassed.

Overall, the proposed face recognition-based AMS provides a more efficient, reliable, and scalable solution to attendance management. By combining image processing and machine learning techniques, this system addresses the shortcomings of traditional and biometric methods, offering an innovative approach the system continuously improves its accuracy over time through machine learning, adapting to new faces and learning from previous interactions. Lastly, the use of cameras and image processing makes the system more scalable and adaptable to various environments, including large classrooms, conferences, or office spaces that improves both accuracy and user experience.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Additionally, determining the attendance status of a specific student on a particular date is a labor-intensive process, requiring extensive searches through multiple documents and archives. These challenges have led to the need for an alternative method that ensures safe and efficient attendance tracking without human intervention. Biometric systems have emerged as a solution, using individuals' fingerprints to record attendance.

A Unimodal Face Recognition System for Automated Class Attendance in IoT-Enabled Educational Environments, This study outlines the design and implementation of an IoT-based attendance system utilizing face recognition, specifically tailored for high school environments. The system integrates the OpenCV library, Python programming, and a Raspberry Pi as the core processing unit. The system leverages haar file object detection and classical machine learning algorithms including eigenfaces

fisherfaces and local binary pattern histograms. A comprehensive methodology is detailed, including flowcharts depicting each phase of the system's operation. Experimental results are analyzed and presented through plots and screenshots. Challenges encountered during the development process are discussed, as well as the system's potential applications and future enhancements. The system aims to automate attendance tracking, enhance the accuracy and security of attendance records, and support student performance monitoring by recording attendance data directly into Google Sheets.

Additionally, the system is designed to operate seamlessly within a classroom setting, reducing manual intervention and minimizing errors associated with traditional attendance-taking methods. By leveraging IoT technology and face recognition, it offers real-time attendance updates, enabling teachers and administrators to access up-to-date records remotely. The use of Google Sheets for data storage ensures easy integration with other educational tools, facilitating further analysis of attendance patterns and trends. The scalability of the system allows for easy expansion to accommodate larger schools or multiple

institutions. Future developments could include integration with student information systems (SIS) for comprehensive performance tracking, real-time notifications for parents or guardians when a student is absent, and advanced data analytics to predict trends in student attendance and engagement. Moreover, improving the system's face recognition accuracy under varying environmental conditions, such as changes in lighting or camera angles, is another area of ongoing research. Overall, the proposed IoT-based class attendance system not only increases efficiency but also contributes to improving educational outcomes by fostering accountability and providing valuable data insights for academic performance and student well-being. Security is another critical aspect of the system. Since student data is sensitive, the implementation ensures secure storage and transmission of attendance records.

Utilizing Neuro evolution-Designed Face Patches for Enhanced Face Recognition in Attendance Systems with Significant Pose Variations [1]. Facial recognition, a type of artificial intelligence, enables a computer to identify individuals [4]. Widespread availability of cameras, facial recognition technology can now be implemented affordably. The facial recognition process involves two main steps. First, the system detects human faces in an image or video, extracts them, and encloses them in bounding boxes. [5].

The system then compares a person's face with the faces stored in its database to recognize and verify their identity. Automating the attendance tracking process was crucial for addressing the challenges posed by traditional methods. Various alternative approaches have been developed to achieve full automate on [6]. This level of automation significantly reduces administrative workload, minimizes the potential for human error, and enhances the overall accuracy of attendance records. Moreover, it provides a secure and efficient way to store and manage attendance data, ensuring that records are not easily lost or tampered with. As a result, facial recognition-based attendance systems are increasingly being adopted in educational institutions to streamline attendance management. modern facial recognition systems are capable of processing data in real-time, allowing for immediate attendance tracking without disrupting the flow of the class.

Andrea Generosi¹ · Thomas Agostinelli¹, Smart retrofitting for human factors: a face recognition-based system proposal [2] On the frontiers of pose invariant face recognition: a review [1], Computer vision systems face a significant challenge in recognizing human faces across varied poses, aiming

to match the natural capacity and capability of human perception. For surveillance applications, pose-invariant face recognition (PIFR) offers a significant advancement by tackling the unique challenge of recognizing faces from different angles. Achieving pose-invariant face recognition is crucial in scenarios where the subject may not always face the camera directly, such as in real-world surveillance or security applications. Traditional face recognition systems struggle with this variability, often requiring subjects to be in frontal poses for accurate identification. However, PIFR aims to overcome these limitations by employing advanced algorithms, deep learning techniques, and 3D modeling to analyze facial features consistently.

Hisahmed Qasim Muhammad Shahzad deep method for face matching current advancements [3] [2], Face recognition is a challenging task, particularly in identifying and detecting an individual's identity accurately. Although extensive work has been conducted in the field of pattern recognition, many issues remain unaddressed in the existing literature. In this research, we present a comparative analysis of three well-known face recognition techniques: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using Eigen faces, The Hidden Markov Model (HMM) combined with Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), and the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) using Gabor filters. These techniques were implemented and evaluated using several metrics, such as the false acceptance rate, false recognition rate, and others. Recent application of multimedia video data method to personnel attendance systems [3] indicates that face identification based access methods control systems are primarily used. rely on devices similar to fingerprint scanners for facial data collection and recognition. However, these systems often suffer from low recognition accuracy, leading to frequent issues in personnel attendance tracking. To address this, our study combines multimedia image and video analysis technology, utilizing multi-angle video capture for attendance monitoring. We employ Shumate's method for preliminary video processing and apply histogram equalization to enhance image quality. Additionally, by using a closing operation, discrete points in the skin color regions are connected, resulting in a more complete and enriched facial region. The system is built on this technological framework. Intelligent Retrofitting for Human Factors: Proposal for a Face Recognition-Based System [4], today, industries are grappling with the challenges of the 'Fourth Industrial Revolution,' commonly referred to as Industry 4.0. This revolution emphasizes new paradigms in manufacturing, such as flexibility, efficiency, safety, digitalization, big data analytics, and interconnectivity. However, the integration of human factors, despite being a core component, is often overlooked. Two of the most neglected aspects are the customization of the worker's user experience and onboard safety. Additionally, integrating cutting-edge technologies into legacy machinery is a critical issue, as it can significantly impact both the economic and environmental management of these machines by extending their life cycle.

Quality-based Representation for Unconstrained Face Recognition [4] significant advances in face recognition have been made over the last decade, largely due to the development of deep learning methods. However, recognizing faces in uncontrolled environments remains a challenging issue for the scientific community. In these settings, the performance of many deep learning-based methods significantly decreases due to the poor quality of face images.

In this work, we propose using an activation map to represent the quality of information in a face image. Different regions of the face are analyzed to assess their quality, and only the high-quality regions are used for recognition with a given deep face model. For the experimental evaluation, three challenging databases were chosen to simulate unconstrained environments: the Labeled Faces in the Wild Database, the Celebrities in Frontal-Profile in the Wild Database, and the AR Database. Three deep face models were used to test the proposed method on these databases, and in every case, the use of the activation map improved the recognition rates of the original models by a range of 0.3% to 31%. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed approach effectively selects face areas with greater discriminative power and sufficient identifying information, while ignoring regions with misleading or irrelevant data. Smart gate unlocking systems have emerged as a confidential and efficient alternative to conventional locking mechanisms. By integrating technologies like face recognition and blink detection, these systems ensure both ease of access and enhanced security. This combination makes unauthorized access difficult, as it goes beyond static image recognition, requiring real-time interaction from the user.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

Face detection techniques then identify and extract faces from these images, which are clustered using a clustering algorithm.

Fig 4. System Architecture

The system creates and updates a training database by matching extracted faces with the database. If a match is found, attendance is marked; if not, new images are added to improve accuracy. This system integrates image processing and machine learning to automate and streamline attendance management, enhancing efficiency and accuracy. A highly accurate automated attendance registration system that combines LBPH (local binary pattern histogram), HOG, and YOLOv7 algorithms. The diagram appears to represent a simple user interface or dashboard for a system.

Admin Login

Here in this module admin can login use system.

Add Students

In this module admin can add students once login at the time of add student add student name, mobile, address and other details also capture real time image using camera

Train Face

Once student faces are captured, the admin must train the system by associating each student's facial image with their corresponding profile in the database. This training process involves the system analyzing and learning the unique facial features of each student, ensuring accurate identification during attendance marking.

Face Matching / Add Attendance

After the system has successfully been trained with student faces, it enters the operational phase where it matches the input faces (from a live webcam feed) with the pre-trained facial data. When a match is found, the system automatically records the student's attendance, eliminating the need for manual input

3.5 Multiple Faces:

The system is designed to capture images of multiple students, typically in a classroom setting. The goal is to recognize each individual face from the group of students for attendance purposes.

3.6 Camera:

A camera is used to capture images of the students. This camera is essential for taking both group images and individual student images for further processing.

3.7 Capture Image:

After the camera captures the images of students, the system requires input of student details, such as their names or IDs, along with the image. This is the registration phase, where the student's facial image is linked to their identity in the system.

3.8 Feature Extraction:

The system performs feature extraction after training. Feature extraction focuses on identifying unique facial characteristics such as the shape of the face, distance between eyes, nose, mouth, and other defining facial landmarks. These features are then stored as a set of numerical values, which make each face unique for the system to recognize. This method achieves an accuracy of 97% by using HOG for feature extraction

3.9 Match Image:

After the dataset is trained, the system is ready for real-time recognition. When an image is captured in the classroom, it compares (matches) the live image with the previously trained dataset of faces. Recognizes the detected face using a trained CNN.

METHODOLOGY

HOG

HOG is Histogram of Oriented Gradients. It is a feature extraction technique commonly used in image processing and computer vision to detect objects by capturing the gradient orientation patterns in localized portions of an image.

Gradient Calculation:

$$G_x = I(x+1,y) - I(x-1,y)$$

$$G_y = I(x,y+1) - I(x,y-1)$$

Where G_x and G_y are the gradients in the x and y directions, respectively, and I is the pixel intensity.

Gradient Magnitude and Orientation:

$$\text{Magnitude} = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2}$$

$$\text{Orientation} = \tan^{-1} (G_y/G_x)$$

Histogram Generation: Each cell generates a histogram of orientations, weighted by gradient magnitudes. The resulting HOG descriptor is a vector representing the image in a lower-dimensional space.

LBPH

Local Binary Pattern Histogram (LBPH) is a popular technique for face recognition, especially effective in scenarios where multiple faces need to be recognized.

LBPH captures the local texture information of facial images by comparing each pixel with its neighbors. This helps in highlighting the features that are crucial for distinguishing different faces. LBPH is relatively invariant to lighting changes, which makes it suitable for recognizing faces under different lighting conditions, an important factor when dealing with multiple faces in varying environments. LBPH is an effective technique for multiple face recognition due to its robustness, efficiency, and ability to capture essential facial features across various conditions.

$$LBP(x, y) = \sum_{i=0}^7 S(I_i - I_c) \cdot 2^i$$

$LBP(x, y)$: This is the Local Binary Pattern value for the pixel at position (x, y).

$\sum_{i=0}^7$: Summation from 0 to 7 because, typically, the LBP compares a pixel to its eight neighbors (in a 3x3 grid around the central pixel).

I_i : Intensity of the i -th neighboring pixel (there are 8 neighbors in total).

I_c : Intensity of the central pixel (the pixel at position (x, y)).

$S(I_i - I_c)$: This is a thresholding function that compares the intensity

YOLOv7

This similar to other versions of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection models, but it is specifically an improvement over previous versions like YOLOv4.

YOLOv5 utilizes a single neural network to predict bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from entire images, distinguishing it from two-stage models. YOLOv5 provides different model sizes—small, medium, and large—to accommodate various hardware capabilities and application requirements.

Bounding Box Predictions: YOLO predicts four values for each bounding box: center coordinates b_x , b_y , width b_w , and height b_h these values are derived as:

$$b_x = \sigma(tx) + cx$$

b_x : The x-coordinate of the bounding box's center.

$\sigma(tx)$: The sigmoid function applied to the predicted x-offset (tx). The sigmoid function ensures the output is between 0 and 1, meaning the predicted offset is localized within a small region.

cx : The x-coordinate of the center of the anchor box (a predefined reference box).

This equation shifts the x-coordinate of the bounding box based on the anchor box position and the predicted offset.

$$b_y = \sigma(ty) + cy$$

b_y : The y-coordinate of the bounding box's center.

$\sigma(ty)$: The sigmoid function applied to the predicted y-offset (ty), limiting it between 0 and 1.

cy : The y-coordinate of the center of the anchor box.

$$b_w = pw \cdot etw$$

b_w : The width of the predicted bounding box.

pw : The width of the anchor box.

etw : The exponential function applied to the predicted width adjustment (tw). This exponential scaling helps refine the width proportionally.

$$b_h = ph \cdot eth$$

b_h : The height of the predicted bounding box.

ph : The height of the anchor box.

eth : The exponential function applied to the predicted height adjustment (th).

YOLOv7 is an advanced, real-time object detection deep learning model that enhances the speed and accuracy of its predecessors. Yolo reformulates classifying objects as directly predicting bound boxes and class prediction from input images.

CNN

CNNs are made up of several layers, such as convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. This structure enables them to automatically learn spatial feature hierarchies from images. CNNs are widely used in various applications, including image classification, object detection, facial recognition, and more

$$f_{ij} = (X * W)_{ij} = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} X(i - m, j + n) \cdot W(m, n)$$

$f_{ij} = (X * W)_{ij}$:

f_{ij} : This is the value of the output feature map at the position (i, j) after applying the convolution.

X: The input image or input feature map.

W: The convolution kernel or filter (a small matrix used to extract features from the input).

$(X * W)_{ij}$: This represents the convolution operation applied to the input image X using the filter W at the position (i, j).

$\sum(m=0 \text{ to } M-1)$:

This summation indicates that the convolution is computed by iterating over all the elements of the filter (kernel). Here, M represents the height or width of the filter (assuming it's a square filter of size MxM).

The convolution operation involves sliding a filter across the input image, element-wise multiplying the filter values with the corresponding image values at each position, and then summing the resulting products to produce a single output value for that position.

$X(i-m, j+n)$:

This represents the value of the input image at a particular pixel (i-m, j+n).

As the filter moves across the image, the filter values are multiplied with these corresponding pixels.

$W(m, n)$:

This is the value of the filter at the position (m, n). The filter typically has small dimensions, like 3x3 or 5x5.

Each value of the filter is multiplied by the corresponding pixel value from the input image.

CNNs are the backbone of deep learning models for image analysis, including face detection and recognition. Deep learn hierarchical representations of data by employing a series of CNN and pooling layers culminating in fully connected layers convolutional layers Fetch features from input images using filters and nonlinear activation functions introduce nonlinearity into the feature maps.

This study employed three methods to train and test the algorithm. All three methods were trained using 2,170 images collected from the students. For testing, we processed a live feed from the camera installed in the classroom. Training was conducted on individual images of the students, while testing was performed on a video showing 31 students, who were registered in the database, sitting. In other words, the training images were entirely different from the test images used in the classroom.

The video also included the lecturer standing at the front of the class, which served to demonstrate the algorithm's ability to accurately detect and identify faces, distinguishing between those registered in the database and those who are not. This capability highlights the system's potential for precise application in universities and schools, without mistakenly assigning random identities to individuals not registered in the database. The first method used the YOLOv7 algorithm to identify and classify faces. The method utilized the HOG algorithm for face recognition, leveraging the Dlib library, which is designed for deep learning applications. This approach depended on machine learning for face detection and deep learning for recognition. However, it struggled to identify two students seated at the far end of the right row. Method employed the Viola-Jones

Algorithm for face detection and LBPH for recognition, making it fully reliant on machine learning. This approach failed to identify one of the female students in the right row. It inaccurately assigned an identity to a lecturer, whose images were not included in the training data, indicating low accuracy for this method.

- Automated Attendance: The system uses face recognition technology to automatically record student attendance as they enter the classroom, eliminating the need for manual roll calls.
- Accuracy and Efficiency: By accurately identifying and verifying each student's face, the system reduces the chances of errors in attendance records, ensuring precise tracking.
- Time-Saving: The automation of the attendance process saves valuable classroom time, allowing teachers and students to focus more on the lesson rather than administrative tasks.
- Seamless Integration: In a smart classroom environment, this system integrates smoothly with other digital tools, contributing to an enhanced and more interactive learning experience.
- Security and Privacy: The system ensures that attendance data is securely stored and accessible only to authorized personnel, maintaining the privacy of students.

Data collection Technique

Camera Installation: High-resolution cameras are installed in the classroom to capture images or videos of students as they enter the room.

Facial Image Capture: The system collects facial images of students in real-time as they pass by the cameras, ensuring that multiple angles and positions are captured for accurate recognition.

Database Integration: Pre-collected facial data of each student is stored in a secure database. This database is used to compare and match the live images captured during each class session.

Real-Time Processing: The captured facial images are processed immediately using face recognition algorithms to identify and verify each student's identity.

Attendance Logging: Once a student is recognized, their attendance is automatically logged into the system's database, creating a record for each session.

Continuous Monitoring: The system may continuously monitor the classroom throughout the session to update attendance records in case a student arrives late or leaves early.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

To eliminate the need for manual attendance recording, an automatic attendance management system is implemented using face detection and recognition techniques. This proposed system enhances the efficiency of existing attendance management systems by reducing the manual effort and burden on lecturers, ensuring accurate attendance tracking. It also decreases the time spent on marking attendance, allowing more time to be devoted to the actual teaching process. In this study, an automated attendance recording system was developed using a deep neural network based on the YOLOv7 architecture, which is highly effective for real-time attendance processing. The proposed method shows promise in streamlining the attendance registration process, outperforming traditional methods used in previous studies.

In the future, we plan to address the aforementioned loopholes in the proposed system. We also aim to enhance the model's structure to improve its performance under various environmental conditions. Additionally, we intend to expand the database by collecting more images featuring different facial expressions and lighting conditions, making it competitive with other databases. The goal is to apply the system to this improved database, preparing it for potential commercial use.

Advanced attendance systems often include features such as real-time tracking, reporting, and analytics, which provide valuable insights into attendance patterns and help institutions make data-driven decisions. Integration with cloud, AI, and Blockchain technologies enhances scalability, privacy, and record integrity, while features like cross-platform compatibility allow for seamless operation across mobile devices, tablets, and computers.

In educational settings, attendance systems can boost productivity by saving time and allowing teachers to focus more on instruction. In workplaces, they support compliance and provide insights into productivity and resource planning. Overall, attendance systems are evolving to become multifunctional tools that not only track attendance but also enhance security, efficiency, and decision-making.

REFERENCES

S. B. Ahmed, S. F. Ali, J. Ahmad, M. Adnan, and M. M. Fraz, "On the frontiers of pose invariant face recognition: a review," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 53, pp. 2571–2634, 2020.

A. Aggarwal, M. Alshehri, M. Kumar, P. Sharma, O. Alfarraj, and V. Deep, “Principal component analysis, hidden markov model, and artificial neural network inspired techniques to recognize faces,” *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, vol. 33, no. 9, p. e6157, 2021.

B. Xu, X. Li, H. Liang, and Y. Li, “Application research of personnel attendance technology based on multimedia video data processing,” *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1–16, 2019.

A. Generosi, T. Agostinelli, and M. Mengoni, “Smart retrofitting for human factors: A face recognition-based system proposal,” *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 421–433, 2023. NSC, “Injury Facts Online. Itasca, Ill.: National Safety Council”. Available at: www.nsc.org. Accessed on 17 December 2001.

N. Nordin and N. M. Fauzi, “A web-based mobile attendance system with facial recognition feature,” 2020.

E. Al Hajri, F. Hafeez, and A. A. NV, “Fully automated classroom attendance system,” *Int. J. Interact. Mob. Technol.*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 95–106, 2019.

A. Kumar, S. Jain, and M. Kumar, “Face and gait biometrics authentication system based on simplified deep neural networks,” *International Journal of Information Technology*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1005–1014, 2023.

R. H. Farouk, H. Mohsen, and Y. M. A. El-Latif, “A proposed biometric technique for improving iris recognition,” *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 79, 2022.